

Digital Writing as a New Tool of the Technological Era

Ilgizarbek Sotimboyev
Student of the WIUT, Uzbekistan

Mokhira Abdullaeva
Associated professor at the IIAU, supervisor, Uzbekistan

Abstract

The study illustrates the benefits of digital writing in modern life. The aim is to analyze the theories related to the digitalization of writing. Since the time when the typewriter was established; almost 3 centuries, scientists have been trying to find out the advantages of typing over handwriting. Digital devices, which allow you to type or text something, really help people in daily life. Many famous people supported the idea of typing in the beginning of the 19th century. However, there are some critics, who hypothesize that digitalization of writing has not changed for good. As technology has started developing in recent times, people cannot quickly become addicted to writing with keyboards, because throughout the many centuries people were writing with pens and pencils.

Keywords: *typewriter, digital devices, keyboards, handwriting.*

Suggested citation: Sotimboyev, I. & Abdullaeva, M. (2024). Digital Writing as a New Tool of the Technological Era. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 1(1), 39-43. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2024.1(1).05

Introduction

Nowadays, in the era of technology, writing has become increasingly intricate and innovative. The realm of digital writing encompasses a wide range of mediums from blog entries to social media updates that allow for unprecedented artistic liberty and individuality. In the beginning of the 19th century, technological development was already starting to spread around the world. After the first typewriter was established, most of the writers firstly avoided the machines because they didn't trust machines, also it was quite expensive, and only wealthy people could have it. However, a well-known American writer Mark Twain was supporting and investing typewriters, because he really believed it was going to spread and ease the life of the people, but the investment unfortunately didn't work as he thought, it wasn't giving a profit to him.

One of the greatest Russian novelists of all time, Lev Tolstoy was one of the first writers, who used a typewriter and honorably evaluated all the advantages of it. The Russian engineer Mikhail Alisov created his own model of typewriter, which was so good that it won many international awards at the end of the 19th century. However, it had only one problem that was concerning potential buyers, and it was the price, because of this, production of Alisov's creation wasn't massive at all.

Literature Review

As the world grows increasingly digitized, digital writing has emerged as an indispensable aspect of modern life. With technological advancements and widespread internet access, digital writing has revolutionized the way we share information and communicate with each other. Reading and writing are two abilities that depend on each other in the early grades. Research on reading has a long tradition, yet writing research is considerably newer. Writing is considered more difficult to control and measure than reading, which means that society knows less today about writing compared with what is known about reading (Aamir, 2019). In March 2022, the researcher from the University of Ferrara, Tania Cerni published a research where they measured and analyzed latency (RTs), the difference between RTs and the acoustic duration of the stimuli (RT-AD), mean length of inter letter intervals (ILIs), and whole response duration (WRD). They further explored the effects of the position of the orthographic complexity on RTs, RT-AD, ILIs, and WRD. Results suggested a cascaded, continuous processing flow for handwriting and a mixed mechanism involving both serial and parallel modes of processing for typing. The differences in linguistic processing during handwriting and typing suggest different mechanisms in segmenting, maintaining, and retrieving the orthographic representation during motor execution (Cerni, 2022). In addition, in 2023, Spilling E, Rønneberg V, Rogne W, Roeser J, and Torrance M. made a natural experiment where they compared development of writing composition skill in five Norwegian first-grade classes in which children (N = 90) learned to compose text by handwriting on paper and in five classes in which children (N = 91) learned by typing on a digital tablet using software that additionally provided read-back via text-to-speech synthesis. Children completed narrative composition probe tasks at five time points over eight months. Students' narratives were evaluated in terms of a range of text features. Statistical analysis was by Bayesian modeling allowing for robust inference in the presence or absence of a modality effect. Children showed improvement in text length, syntactic accuracy and complexity, and narrative sophistication. However, the rate of improvement was unaffected by modality. Spelling and spacing, which were directly supported by read-back functionality in the digital condition, improved just in the handwriting condition, with better performance but no improvement in the digital condition (Spilling, et al., 2023).

In 2014, Anne Chemin, a journalist for *Le Monde*, said that some states, such as Indiana, have decided to go on teaching cursive writing in school. Without this skill, they assert, young Americans will no longer be able to read birthday cards from their grandparents, comments by teachers on their assignments or the original, handwritten text of the constitution and the Declaration of Independence (Chemin, 2014). I think that all views of these authors on the impact of digitalisation are enough to support the fact that digitalization is a change for good. This view of calling the papers irrelevant nowadays is a correct point, as written papers cannot be better than typing documents in saving time, quality, and copying.

Tania Cerni and Remo Job made an experiment, where all the participants performed two dictation tasks: the handwriting task and the typing task, with separated blocks of words and pseudo words. The order of the tasks was counterbalanced between participants, half starting with the pen and half with the keyboard. Within each task, half of the participants started with the word list and the other half with the pseudo word list.

All participants performed the tasks individually in the presence of the experimenter in a quiet laboratory of the University of Trento. They sat in front of a tablet PC (see Equipment) and were encouraged to take a comfortable position, self-regulating the distance from the screen. No time limits were imposed, but participants were encouraged to write/type fast and accurately each stimulus as they heard it. In the typing task, on each trial, an auditory stimulus, either a word or a pseudo word, was presented. The participant typed it on the keyboard and, when finished, he/she pressed the Return key to hear the next stimulus. In this way, the end of the trial was self-regulated.

As soon as the trail finished, the next one started. The typed letters appeared at the center of the screen. Participants were instructed to avoid the use of the backspace key. The backspace key was not disabled but, to discourage its usage, participants were informed that pressing it would be accounted as an error.

Before the beginning of the task, four practice trials ensured that participants understood the procedure and familiarized themselves with the keyboard. In the handwriting task, the stimuli and the trial structure were the same as the typing task. Participants handwrote in uppercase letters on a line at the center of the screen, using a special pen (see Equipment) (Cerni, & Job, 2022). Ose Askvik E, Van Der Weel F, and Van Der Meer A, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, found that when writing by hand using a digital pen on a touchscreen, brain areas in the parietal and central regions showed event-related synchronized activity in the theta range. Existing literature suggests that such oscillatory neuronal activity in these particular brain areas is important for memory and for the encoding of new information and, therefore, provides the brain with optimal conditions for learning. When drawing, we found similar activation patterns in the parietal areas, in addition to event-related desynchronization in the alpha/beta range, suggesting both similarities but also slight differences in activation patterns when drawing and writing by hand. When typewriting on a keyboard, we found event-related desynchronized activity in the theta range and, to a lesser extent, in the alpha range in parietal and central brain regions. However, as this activity was desynchronized and differed from when writing by hand and drawing, its relation to learning remains unclear. For 12-year-old children, the same activation patterns were found, but to a lesser extent. We suggest that children, from an early age, must be exposed to handwriting and drawing activities in school to establish the neuronal oscillation patterns that are beneficial for learning. We conclude that because of the benefits of sensory-motor integration due to the larger involvement of the senses as well as fine and precisely controlled hand movements when writing by hand and when drawing, it is vital to maintain both activities in a learning environment to facilitate and optimize learning (Askvik, et al., 2020).

Methodology

Most of the experiments were conducted by dividing students or people into 2 groups: 1 group typed and read on computer and the other group was focused on both writing and reading on paper. However, most of the experiments were focused on different kind of aspects, for instance, some of them mainly evaluated the brain activity in both writing on paper and typing, and some of them even made an experiment with children by focusing how they did the task and by checking the accuracy, spelling, and spacing. Hence, all the experiments about typing vs handwriting, focused on different things.

In that experiment of Tania Cerni and Remo Job, to proceed to the next trial, they pressed the pen on a virtual button representing a red arrow placed at the right of the line. Participants were encouraged to lift the pen naturally between letters as commonly done in writing in uppercase. Four practice trials were administered before the task to allow participants to familiarize themselves with the pen on the screen and with the lifting movement between letters. Uppercase letters separated by spaces were used to allow the calculation of inter letter intervals (see a similar procedure in e.g., Kandel et al., 2006) (Cerni, & Job, 2022).

Discussion

The aim of the studies was to point some evidence that with digitalization more and more people and even children can work and study accurately, as many of the experiments, which were focused

on different areas, proved that typing can be be at the same time beneficial - not doing any accuracy mistakes - and also less beneficial for the development of the part in young people's brains. Writing has become an essential component of modern life, and we see it in various forms of digital communication such as social media, email, texts, and blog articles. Digital writing is significant not just for its practicality but also its ability to encourage creativity and personal expression. Also, digitized writing can be accessible for everyone with different languages, as they can be translated, in addition, Digital optimization is optimized for different devices, and across can be read anywhere in apps, browsers e.g. In jobs such as teaching and administrative jobs, usually people write on computers or on devices where they can type their presentations or reports. According to the touch screen experiment, the researchers Ose Askvik E, Van Der Weel F, and Van Der Meer A concluded that when group of young people draw something on the screen, there were activation patterns in the parietal areas. In other word, they are the important parts of the brain that allow humans to analyze and understand the reality, which they see; surprisingly, activation patterns in the parietal areas were not only noticed during the time when participants drew, but also when participants wrote by hand. However, typing had not the same result as touch screen drawing and writing by hand, even though activation patterns happened in parietal areas of the brain, but it was mush lesser. Basically, activation patterns were in both parietal and central areas of the brain, but not as much. Obviously, it really contradicts the view of typing over handwriting, I agree that in young ages it is essential to paint and write with their hands in order to develop the essential parts of the brain, while with typing, it is impossible for children's brains to be developed fully, like with writing and painting. However, not everyone needs extra ordinary activation patterns in the brain, after growing up peoples' brains will once stop the development, and there is no way to make it continue or generate the patterns in areas of the brain. No pens, no drawing on the screen, even no typing can make it happen, so people should live their life by solving the problems with the easiest and not time consuming ways. It is obviously saying that rather than writing on the paper by hand, with making a dirt on the paper or with incoherent handwriting with bunch of accuracy mistakes, it is much more convenient to write it by just touching the buttons with letters, and when something is incorrect people can go just to the part, where they have mistaken, and erase the wrong part and retyping it again. But making a point that handwriting should be stopped to be taught in schools is completely incorrect view, as for many centuries human beings became intelligent, because the wrote and draw by hands, which can assist to conclude that for the development of the young people's brains it is more beneficial to write and draw by hands.

Conclusion

All in all, digital writing is a key thing for interactivity. As in handwriting we cannot add any links from the browsers, social media, in other words, features from the internet. However, with the help of the internet it can be possible. Anything related to the typed documents on the internet can be found anywhere by anyone, but regarding the handwritten papers or documents, they can only be found in the libraries, which are really rare nowadays. Since the 19th century digital writing has become an essential part of the human's life. Many jobs were established, which are all about writing such as documents, copying documents, administrators and so on. With the help of computer science, writing has become way more innovative. In social media, people started to share information with others. Digital writing offers a great variety of opportunities, which can't be matched with the pen-pencil method of writing. In the beginning, it is a bit complex to adapt to digital writing, as all of us are in the first stage of writing "novices", but then slowly we become the apprentices. But also, if we practice more and gain more experience, we can be in the 3rd stage of writing "the Masters".

References

- Aamir, S. (2019). Handwriting vs typing: Which one is better? *The Startup*. Retrieved from <https://medium.com/swlh/handwriting-v-s-typing-which-one-is-better-fc211606aff6>
- Askvik, E. O., Van Der Weel, F., & Van Der Meer, A. (2020). The importance of cursive handwriting over typewriting for learning in the classroom: A high-density EEG study of 12-year-old children and young adults. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34326.18702>
- Cerni, T. (2022). The interaction of central and peripheral processes in typing and handwriting: A direct comparison. *PsyArXiv Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/y5f92>
- Cerni, T., & Job, R. (2022). The interaction of central and peripheral processes in typing and handwriting: A direct comparison. *PsyArXiv Preprints*, 15-16. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/y5f92>
- Chemin, A. (2014). Writing vs typing: Is the pen still mightier than the keyboard? *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2014/dec/16/cognitive-benefits-handwriting-decline-typing>
- Spilling, E., Rønneberg, V., Rogne, W., Roeser, J., & Torrance, M. (2023). Writing by hand or digitally in first grade: Effects on rate of learning to compose text. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36843.48971>

